

Reducing Scraps in Roving Process of Car Headliner Manufacturing

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Abstract – In car headliner manufacturing industry large number of glass fiber gets wasted in the roving process. The aim is to reduce the scraps and decrease the cost. For the manufacturing of a headliner several steps are to be done. Among that roving is a process which is for spreading glass fibers on the PU slice and Crinkle paper. Glass fibers are spreader on the PU slice and Crinkle paper through the spillages from the roving bundle. From the spillage the glass fiber passes into the cutter and cut into pieces and falls on the PU slices and Crinkle paper. But PU slice and Crinkle paper vary in their dimension in the width. So some amount of fibers gets wasted when PU slice passes. Here single acting cylinder arrangement is used for reducing scraps in the roving process. The project is that when cylinder gets extended it arrests the glass fiber movement in the spillage. When cylinder gets retracted it leaves the fiber from the spillage. The excess waste falling in the PU slice gets saved by implementing the project.

Keywords: Glass fiber, Roving Process, Headliner, PU- Poly Urethane, Crinkle paper.

I. Introduction

To reduce the scrap in the headliner manufacturing industries was important one [7]. To analysis each and every manufacturing process and find the process which can be reduce the scrap. This paper deals with the manufacturing process of headliner and the modification. The modification is implementing to the manufacturing process then monitoring the scrape removal percentage.

II. Headliner

A composite materials is used for the headliner to adhered to the inside roof of automobiles or yachts. Multilayered composite materials used to produce Headliners by the process of together the multilayered, including the requested look, feel, stiffness, and sound reduction needed in cars [1]. Automotive headliner is optimized with respect to head impact counter measure or to integrate additional LED lighting film behind the fabric [2]. Nylon or vinyl materials are usually used to make Car Headliners and dimensions of various headliners are given in Table 1. The material can come in any color and it is usually porous or perforated to allow moisture to seep through [3]. There is also foam underneath the headliner which is part of the car interior. Headliners parts are shown in Fig. 1 and also have plastic rivets to attach them to the ceiling.

II.1. Roving

A long and narrow bundle of fiber is known as Roving. To produced spun yam, raw cotton or other fibers the Roving is used [4]. The fibers lie roughly parallel in smooth bundles after carding. By hand or machine the fiber are drawn out, and slightly twisted to form lengths suitable for spinning [5]. These un spun strands of fiber are the roving. Roving can also mean a roll of these strands, the strands in general (as a mass noun), or the process of creating them [6].

TABLE 1
DIMENSIONS OF VARIOUS HEADLINERS

MODEL	CRINKLE PAPER	PU SLICE
	LENGTH*WIDTH(mm)	LENGTH*WIDTH(mm)
ACCENT	1650*1250	1600*1200
SANTRO	1780*1260	1765*1220
i10	1750*1250	1740*1220
SUNNY	1850*1350	1840*1320
MICRA	1900*1400	1840*1350
FIESTA	1850*1400	1840*1350
INNOVA	1880*1350	1820*1280
COROLLA	1950*1350	1870*1280

Fig.1 Head Liner part

Fig. 3 Before implementation

III. Scraps Wasted Before Implementation of Design

Based on the analysis taken in the industry, we observed that Normally due to the timing of the sensor actuation lot of glass fibers gets wasted. It can be rectified only by observing the sensor timing.

Total glass fiber wasted in 1 hour: 3.025 kg

Total glass fiber wasted in a day: 72.6 kg

Glass fiber cost Rs.65 per kg.

So total cost wasted per day: Rs. 4719

So total cost wasted per month: Rs. 141570

Glass fibers are spreader on the PU slice and Crinkle paper through the spillages from the roving bundle. From the spillage the glass fiber passes into the cutter and cut into pieces and falls on the PU slices and Crinkle paper. The size of PU slice is 50mm lesser than the crinkle paper. The glass fibers get wasted when PU slice passes. When crinkle paper pass through the glass fibers it does not wasted. Fig. 3 shows the before modification of single acting cylinder.

Fig 2. Working hrs vs wastage (kg)

Fig. 2 shows that a large amount of glass fibers was wasted during the production of the headliner in the roving process. In a day approximately 70 to 80 kilograms gets wasted.

III.1. Modification

Roving spreader is a process of spilling fiber glass on both crinkle paper and PU slices for stiffness. Fiber glass material are stored in the form of bundles in the platform and cut into small pieces of length 55mm by means of cutter roller. The roving are fed to the cutter through tubes with an inner dia of 16mm. These modifications are shown in Fig. 4. The roving are blown through the tubes to cutter by use of compressed air gun. For insertion of roving open safety hood and feed roving under feeder roller, that roving can be pulled off by the contact roll.

We used single acting cylinder for saving the glass fiber. When PU slice passes the cylinder gets extended towards the spillage so that movement of glass fiber via the spillage gets arrested. And when the crinkle paper passes the cylinder gets retracted away from the spillage so fiber gets free movement. Normally glass fibers are used for the stiffness of the headliner. Also it resists temperature and does not allow heat inside the car. The modified design are implemented in the system and shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4 CADD Design of the modification

Fig. 5 After Implementation

Fig. 6 working hrs.vs wastage (kg)

Based on the analysis taken in the roving process a large amount of scraps gets saved after implementation.

- ✓ Glass fiber saved per Headliner: 20 grams
- ✓ Glass fiber saved per hour: 1200 grams
- ✓ Cost of 1 kg of glass fiber: Rs.65
- ✓ So cost saved per hour: Rs.78
- ✓ Cost saved per day: Rs.1872
- ✓ Cost saved per month: Rs.56, 160

The analysis taken after implementing the project shows that a lot amount of wastages (ie) scraps gets saved. Here approximately 50 kilograms gets wasted. By reducing the scraps certain amount of cost is being saved. After implementation of the process the variation in working Hours and wastages are shown in Fig. 6.

IV. Conclusion

After it is observed that from the above test conditions and results, for the given vertical corrugated fills with calculated Ka value, yields 58.00% efficiency at a fill height of 1m. If it modified to the height of 1.2m, the efficiency of the tower increased to 60.60%. Above 1.2m, as the resistance to air flow increased considerably affecting the performance of the tower. The result is validated with density of the VCP fills.

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